

EFFECTIVE TECHNIQUES TO DEVELOP COMMUNICATION SKILLS OF INTERMEDIATE LEVEL LEARNERS

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Abstract

This article focuses on how to develop communication skills of intermediate level learners. There are such effective techniques discussed as error treatment, and integration of speaking with other skills of English. First and foremost, the reason that hinders students ability to speak is shyness which is proven with a pie chart in the article.

Key words: error treatment, critical thinking, integration, receptive skills, productive skills, communication skills, communicative approach

According to the objectives of the current study, we investigated that speaking is considered to be more essential by learners compared to any other skills. The current research plays a great role in guiding future teachers to use interactive activities and innovative strategies to enhance the communicative skills of intermediate level students. The suggested methods are integrating speaking with receptive skills, and positive error treatment strategies.

However fluent B1 students may seem, there are several factors that hinders the development of their verbal competence. The main reasons can be poor error treatments, and boring grammar translation method. This is due to the fact that confidence and competence usually lead to strengths of English-speaking skills. Patil (2008) asserted that building up the learner's confidence to eliminate fear of making errors was a priority that the teacher should consider in order to make the learner feel comfortable with their language use. Many learners hesitate to talk in class because they have a lot of anxiety about making mistakes, especially in front of their peers. According to a recent survey, intermediate level of students are shy in English communication. This survey was carried out among intermediate levels only. This quantitative data proves that poor error correction may result in their shyness.

Are you shy to speak (in English) in front of people?

160 responses

Although shyness looks usual, teachers come across a lot of difficulties as to how to correct their students' mistakes without embarrassing them in a class. If their teacher continues giving only negative feedbacks or keep finding and telling the errors they make during their oral interaction, this may lead them to be a passive student next time. To begin with, we have decided to give some notions about error treatments which may save student from too much embarrassment.

Suggested error treatment techniques to mitigate shyness

Rationale for Error Correction

- Error correction is part of the teaching and learning process.
- If error correction is done correctly, it helps students discover knowledge and follow their unique individual learning paths.
- Over-correction/ poor correction techniques can be demotivating for learners. They may lead to learners losing interest in learning and speaking the language.
- It is important that teachers make good decisions about what, when and how to correct errors to be able to best assist their learners in acquiring speaking skills (Loewen, 2007).

What Errors to Correct?

Fluency vs. Accuracy

- Speaking English with a high level of accuracy means to speak correctly, with very few mistakes.
- Speaking English with a high level of fluency means to speak easily, quickly and with few pauses.

• Ideally, one would speak both accurately and fluently, but it takes time to practice. Teachers can focus on either fluency or accuracy in different speaking activities. It depends on the purpose of the activity and learner’s proficiency level. When to Correct Errors?

- Fluency: In communicative language teaching, we should first value the meaning and message learners produce.
- Focus on errors that effect the meaning of the message.
- Accuracy: When students are practicing new words or trying to improve pronunciation, you might correct more specific errors, based on what they are learning.

Some Error Correction Techniques:

- Use body language. For example, make a ‘T’ with fingers to illustrate missing ‘the’ or cross hands over to show wrong word order (Mumford & Darn, 2005)
- Use facial expressions. For example, raise your eyebrow, tilt your head, give a slight frown
- Repeat what they are saying wrong to give students an opportunity to correct themselves (Nunan, 2003).
- Say it the right way and give students an opportunity to repeat the correct language.
- Point at correct language. Have grammar rules, vocabulary, or structure written on the board and point out to them if a student is making a mistake.

How to integrate receptive skills with speaking

As it is visible from the chart is that most of the learners want to improve their speaking skills rather than other skills. However, all skills have their essence in learning a language.

Can you use the grammar structure you have just learned? (can you make sentences with that structure in speaking?)
160 responses

We investigated how to integrate speaking skills with other skills of English. Speaking integrated with other language skills to develop interactive and effective oral communication skills in ESL classroom, it is also important to know how speaking skills are related with the other English skills (listening, writing, and reading), and how the features of other English skills can develop speaking skills in the speaking process. Activities in language learning involve the use of the skills of listening, speaking, reading, and writing. These skills cannot be practiced in isolation.

We tried conducting speaking in relation to the productive skill of writing.

There are a number of stages of the Writing Process. It is effective if a teacher facilitates pre-warm-up activities so that students will be able have better insight into what type of writing they are doing and brainstorm ideas. First of all, a teacher should be clearly aware of the stages of writing to explain it.

- Developing ideas (pre- writing)
- Drafting
- Revising
- Editing
- Sharing/Publishing

For example, if the topic is “Do the advantages of the internet outweigh the disadvantages?”, the teacher should divide the group into two (A group for advantages, B one for drawbacks) this can be a huge debate which enables students to share their ideas orally, try to support their answers, provide examples to fight against the opposite side. Hence, they will easily brainstorm ideas to write. From psychological perspective, the competitive environment makes them think and speak quickly which is a clever way of developing communication skills of students coupled with writing skills.

The way we conducted Speaking in Relation to the Receptive Skill of Reading:

In order to carry on both skills, engage learners in reading activities

- Teach learners how to interact with their thoughts while reading.
- Engage them in discussion about the reading with other learners

In before reading activity they should read the title only and try to make predictions about the reading and its context. Without reading the text, indicate the structural component in which the theme is expressed. Read this part of the text, name the topic. In during activity retell what they have understand so far, make more predictions, ask questions from each other. After reading they should retell and summarize what they have understood from the text. Reading comprehension exercises. Say what questions are discussed in the text. Say what the problem is from the content. Put a few questions to the text and ask them to your friend, then answer his questions. Confirm the point of view stated in the text using your own example. Express your opinion on what you have read. Provide any additional information you know. Give examples, facts similar to those described in the article. The more they speak, the more they understand the reading.

Speaking in Relation to the Receptive Skill of Listening

It has been found effective that Pre-listening, While listening, and Post-listening activities are instrumental in both making listening more comprehensible and integrating speaking with it.

Pre-listening activity:

- Discuss relevant experiences
- Associate vocabulary with the topic
- Predict information about the topic

While listening:

- Identify supportive details about the topic
- Answer questions
- Complete sentences
- Complete a chart, map, graph, notes page, etc.

Post listening:

- Give opinions (using English language functions)
- Relate similar experiences
- Write a brief report
- Debate the topic

Results of communicative competence of B1 level students

The outcome of assessment provides information about students' progress in speaking and evaluates the appropriateness of teacher's selection of speaking strategies. Using these all strategies above proven effective according to our speaking test results. Besides being a hypothesis, our research statement proved

itself to be correct. Although some subjects did not show any improvements, the majority of them developed because of the other group mates' influences.

	Names and ages	Pre-test results	Progress-test results	Post-test results	Improve ments
1	Sa'dullayeva, 18	4	6	8	Excellent
2	To'rayeva, 17	4	8	8	Exellent
3	Ibrokhimova, 15	5	5	5	No
4	Shamsiyev, 16	5	6	6	Better
5	Abbosova, 21	6	7	8	Excellent
6	Shomurodova, 20	8	9	10	Excellent
7	Makhmarajabova, 19	8	8	10	Excellent
8	Tohirova, 19	7	9	9	Excellent
9	Mirshokhidova, 18	5	5	7	Better
10	Sharipova 16	6	7	7	Better

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